

INTERNAL AUDIT SERVICE IN JOINT STOCK COMPANIES IMPROVEMENT

Turumova Dildora Abdumannonovna

*Teacher of the "Economics and Management" department of Jizzakh Polytechnic
Institute*

dildoraturumova1985@gmail.com

Payzimurodova Maftuna Shavkat qizi

Student of Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute

maftunashavkatovna7@gmail.com

Abstract: Internal audit - financial and financial status of joint-stock companies is a type of service that allows close inspection, its main function regularly informing the company's supervisory board about its activities consists of standing. The advantages of an internal audit service are that it is a company is to quickly identify the shortcomings and problems that may arise in the activity and provide a solution to it. In this thesis, we consider the issues related to the organization of the internal audit service in the joint-stock companies of our country.

Key words: audit, internal audit, internal control, joint-stock companies, commerce.

Internal audit in current conditions as the digital economy develops. There are several tasks of the service, such as being an active participant in the management of companies, continuous monitoring of their activities, regular monitoring of it through information and communication technology tools, providing analysis and planning of organizational and economic decisions, evaluating the results of its activities.

Therefore, it is important to organize control forms that are consistent and fully compatible with the business conditions, as well as minimize the problems and risks that may arise in the activities of joint-stock companies, in particular, the unique work methodology and techniques of internal audit requires continuous improvement. This is the further improvement of the joint-stock companies of our country effective audit and analysis of problems directly related to this activity organization, solving them based on scientific views is of particular importance. All these objective processes require further improvement of the methodology of internal audit in joint-stock companies, research of its theoretical and organizational problems based on the market economy, similar to the free economy. The company's

modern internal control system, which includes internal audit services, is one of the indispensable management tools in the organization of corporate management and control. Based on the above, he determined the direction and relevance of the subject of this research work.

It is known that the need to use world experience in the development of all sectors in our country is constantly being emphasized, in particular auditing activities as well. In this regard, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev's decision "On measures for the further development of auditing activities in the Republic of Uzbekistan"[1] and the law "On auditing activities"[2] established the organization of auditing activities based on international standards. The task of improving the audit is the responsibility of local audit firms international in increasing competitiveness, standardization of auditing activities compliance with auditing standards. International professional standards of internal auditing.

As one of the components of the IPPF, the International Professional Practice Framework, these standards are set out as principles and provide a framework for the organization of the internal audit service.

Figure 1. Factors increasing the efficiency of the internal audit service.*

*Author development based on data

Effectiveness in improving internal audit in joint-stock companies international standards are one of the important factors. In this regard international internal audit standards as well as external audit standards are considered important. International standards provide auditors with sufficient guidance on the processes that must be performed before relying on the work of internal auditors in assessing individual components of internal audit quality.

Professionalism of internal auditors in improving the effectiveness of internal audit, that is, they have a high level of knowledge and many years of experience.

"Internal auditors are also included in the International Professional Standards of Internal Auditing it is established that they should have the necessary knowledge, skills and other powers to perform their duties." [3]

One of the most important aspects of internal audit is the development of new projects identify any risks anticipated in exiting and implementing them and analysis, making proposals and recommendations that allow to reduce the level of these risks and the damage they cause.

At the same time, the internal audit service monitors the expenditures for these projects and programs, checks the company's financial and management reports, their truthfulness and timely and effective implementation. The internal audit service assesses the contracts concluded between the parties and their fulfillment of their obligations. It is also involved in the evaluation of the control system within the framework of information and communication technologies, which has been implemented and is being introduced.

Internal auditing is a significant cost to the company in pursuit of its goals not to be related to, the evidence about the company's financial situation and sufficient accumulation in the formation of opinions, created in the process of consideration should increase the value of information and be based on common sense.

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